

Are you working on a **solution** for **Transitional Care** or **Clinical Pathways**?

Apply to our Open Call

Boost your chances for success and smooth your **path to market!**

EVOLVE2CARE will finance up to **€5K in Living Lab services** such as:

Co-creation | User Engagement | Product Validation | Access to Data & Infrastructure

Use Cases

Hospital Discharge
Management

Remote Monitoring and
Home-Based Care

Inclusive Technologies for
Aging and Chronic Care

If your solution is linked to one of the Use Cases scan the QR code and apply to the EVOLVE2CARE Open Call!

Discover more at:
www.evolve2care.eu

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